

Reconfigurable frequency discriminator with uniform 2-bit frequency band using slow wave structure

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In this paper, we conducted a design and simulation for a reconfigurable frequency discriminator (RFD) with a slow wave structure and a 180° silicon MEMS phase shifter. The RFD, which can obtain radio information used by enemy forces, is a key device in electronic warfare [1]. Typically, the RFD is composed of power divider, reference line, delay lines, and power combiner [1]. An RF input signal is split into two signals of equal magnitude by a power divider. The signals of the reference line and delay line are delayed and recombined at the circuit output to extract bits for unknown frequency identification. The recombined signal is divided into frequency sub-bands, used for frequency identification. PIN diodes are typically used to select the delay line in RFD, however it consumes high power and has limited application at high frequencies [2].

Electronic warfare applications frequently use high frequency bands, requiring accurate frequency discrimination from the RFD. However, it is necessary to study the RFD design for precise and uniform frequency discrimination to be applied at high frequency bands, because PIN diodes have limitations at high frequencies. In order to solve the limitation of PIN diodes, the reconfigurable delay line was designed and simulated using a MEMS 180° phase shifter, actuated by electrostatic force replacing the PIN diodes. A slow wave structure is used to increase group delay and electrically reduce the long transmission line. Therefore, the reference line of the RFD is designed using a slow wave structure that can be fabricated shorter than a typical transmission line and is used to tune the frequency response of the device.

Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram of the proposed 2-bit RFD based on CPW transmission lines. The input and output port impedances were matched to 50 Ω and a 2-stage power divider is used operating at 30-40 GHz. The length of the reference line has one-half of the guided wavelength at 35 GHz. The silicon MEMS phase shifter changes the capacitance of the reconfigurable delay line to achieve a 180° phase difference between its two states, on and off at 35 GHz. Figure 2 shows the HFSS simulation results of the proposed device. The RFD design using a typical CPW line had a non-uniform 2-bit distribution of the frequency sub-bands (see black line in Fig. 2). The characteristic impedance of the reference line was adjusted through the slow wave structure to obtain uniform frequency sub-bands for frequency identification. The frequency sub-bands of the RFD can be uniformly discriminated in range from 32 GHz to 40 GHz, when the characteristic impedance of the reference line is tuned 71.9 Ω (see red line in Fig. 2). As a result, we verified that the slow wave structure can be used to obtain uniform frequency sub-bands for frequency identification in the 32-40 GHz band.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of RFD

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of RFD

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